

Continental mid-lithosphere discontinuity: a water collector during craton evolution

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1. Dataset of the reference model in Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5a, Figure S3, Figure S4, Figure S5, Figure S6, Figure S7

Model-M1.zip

2. Datasets of other models as summarized in Table S6, Figure 5b, 5c, Figure S10

Model-M2.zip

Model-M3.zip

Model-M4.zip

Model-M5.zip

Model-M6.zip

Model-M7.zip

3. Datasets of comparison models in Figure S8, Figure S9

Model-other-FigS8.zip

Model-other-FigS9.zip

4. Dataset of the nature of the MLD in Figure 1

Database-MLD.zip

5. Dataset of the water capacity of mantle rock and shear-wave velocity (V_s) in

Figure S1, Figure S2, Figure S11

Database-Wt.zip

Database-Vs.zip